

A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Simulation Technique on Knowledge and Practice Related to Stoma Care Among Staff Nurses Working in Selected Hospital of Bhopal (MP)

*Megha Joshi, **Babita Agrawal, ***Rekha R Gupta

*Post Graduate Student, Department of Medical Surgical Nursing, **Professor, Department of Medical Surgical Nursing, ***Professor, Department of Child Health Nursing, People's College of Nursing and Research Centre, People's University, Bhanpur, Bhopal

ABSTRACT

Stoma care is a procedure that provides care for stoma patients. The nurse need to have adequate knowledge and practice in stoma care nursing. Simulation technique is very effective tool to increase the knowledge and practice related to stoma care in staff nurses. The purpose of the study was to assess the effectiveness of the Simulation technique to increase knowledge & skill related to Stoma care among staff nurses working in selected hospital. A Quasi-experimental research design and qualitative evaluation approach was used. The sample consisted of 40 staff nurses using a purposive sampling technique. The mean post-test knowledge score of staff nurses was 18.0250 and the standard deviation was 3.07586 and the mean pre-test knowledge score was 7.6250 and the standard deviation was 4.16756. The computed 't' value ('t'=2.02) and the mean post-test practice score of staff nurses was 8.9250 and standard deviation was .99711 and mean pre-test practice score was 4.0750 and the standard deviation was 2.24622. The computed 't' value ('t'= 2.02) was significant at 0.05 level of significance. It is concluded that the marked difference was seen in the mean knowledge and practice score before and after the administration of the simulation, the technique was effective in improving the knowledge and practice level of staff nurses regarding stoma care.

KEY WORDS: Simulation technique, knowledge, practice, stoma care, staff nurses

INTRODUCTION:

In India, there are over 50,000 stoma patients in the county and 350 stoma cases come every year and they are referred from other hospitals. This stoma patient really needs post-operative care they want a good practitioner nurse with good knowledge and practice regarding stoma care^[1].

The Western Australian Ostomy Association states that there are 3 million ostomates in the world. Globally ostomy /stoma care was valued at USD 2.81 billion in 2018 and is projected to reach USD 4.23 billion by 2026, ostomy is gradually becoming a widely accepted procedure like a colostomy, ileostomy, tracheotomy, and urostomy^[2].

In North America state 1,20,000 stoma care procedure are performed every year and people of all age groups has the possibility of the formation of a stoma. The stoma-related complications are 26.5% (20-100) and the highest complications incidence rate in colostomy is approximately 62.6% (20-100) %^[3].

The stoma is surgically created opening for the purpose. The sites includes the esophagus, stomach, duodenum, ileum, colon, pleural cavity, ureters, urinary, bladder, and renal pelvis. The stoma may be temporary or permanent. The surgical procedure that should create an artificial stoma has called Ostomy^[4].

A stoma is a surgically created opening of a body and there are increasing number of cases of stomas, correspondingly the need for specialized nurses for helping patients with a stoma has increased. Stoma nurses have specialized knowledge and skill to render care to patients with stoma^[5].

A stoma nurse must have adequate and good skills in order to provide high-quality care. On the job training & short term courses are help full to develop skill related to stoma care.

Corresponding Author:

Ms Megha Joshi

Post Graduate Student, Department of
Medical Surgical Nursing,
People's College of Nursing &
Research Centre,

People's University, Bhopal - 462037

Phone No.: 09302389536

E-mail: meghajoshi9302@gmail.com

Simulation techniques are used to provide good knowledge and required skill to nurses in order to get desired patient outcomes related to stoma care^[6-7].

OBJECTIVES:

- To assess the knowledge and practice among staff nurses regarding Stoma Care.
- To provide knowledge and enhance skill related to stoma care by simulation technique to the staff nurses in selected clinical setting.
- To assess the knowledge and practice of staff nurses working in related to Stoma Care among selected clinical setting.
- To correlate post test and pre test scores of knowledge & skill related to stoma care among staff nurses of selected clinical setting.

HYPOTHESES:

H₀: There will be no significant difference between the pre-test and the post-test score after the implementation of simulation technique on knowledge and practice related to stoma care among staff nurses working in selected hospital.

H₁: There will be a significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores after the implementation of simulation techniques on knowledge and practice related to stoma care among staff nurses working in selected hospital.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A Quasi-experimental research design and quantitative evaluative approach is used. The sample consisted of 40 staff nurses, purposive sampling technique was used and the sampling criteria followed. The Ethical Clearance was taken. The conceptual framework used for the study was Imogene King's theory of goal attainment. The tool used for data collection was self-structured knowledge questionnaires and practice checklists to assess the knowledge and practice, the investigator administered a simulation technique related to knowledge and practice on stoma care among staff nurses working in selected hospital. Independent variables refers to providing simulation techniques related to stoma care among staff nurses and dependent variable refers to knowledge and practice regarding stoma care. A structured questionnaire was developed as the tool and structural/content validity obtained from experts.

The pilot study was conducted before the main study.

DISCUSSION:

Table 1 figure 1 reveals the comparison of the

mean of the pre-test and post-test scores among the staff nurses. The percentage distribution in pre-test was (62.5%) had poor knowledge and in post-test (5.0%) had poor knowledge in staff nurses. In the pre-test were (25.0%) average and in Post-test (7.5%) had average knowledge. In the pre-test (5.0%) had adequate and in post-test (87.5%) had adequate knowledge.

Table 1: Distribution of Knowledge pre-test and post-test score according to frequency and percentage (n=40).

Knowledge	Pre-test		Post-test	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Poor	25	62.5	2	5.0
Average	10	25.0	3	7.5
Adequate	5	12.5	35	87.5
Total	40	100.0	40	100.0

Figure 1: Frequency distribution of the Knowledge pre-test and Post score related to Stoma Care among Nurses.

Table 2: Distribution of Practice pre-test and post-test score (n=40).

Practice	Pre-test		Post-test	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Poor	22	55.0	0	0.0
Average	14	35.0	4	10.0
Adequate	4	10.0	36	90.0
Total	40	100.0	40	100.0

Table 2 and figure 2 reveals that: Represents the comparison of the mean of the pre-test post-test test scores among the staff nurses. Percentage distribution the in pre-test were (55.0%) had poor practice and in post-test (5%) had poor practice staff nurses. In the pre-test were (35.0%) average and in Post-test (10.0%) had average practice. In pre-test (10.0%) had adequate and

Table 3: Shows the difference between the Knowledge pre-test and post-test mean and standard deviation (N=40).

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean difference	t value	df	Tabulated value	Significance
Pre-test	7.63	4.16	10.40	14.09	39	2.02	Significant at P=0.05
Post-test	18.03	3.07		3			

Table 4: Shows the difference between Practice pre-test and post-test mean and standard deviation (N=40).

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	t value	df	Tabulate d value	Significance
Pre test	4.08	2.24622	4.85	12.04	39	2.02	Significant at p=0.05
Post test	8.75	.99711		1			

in post-test (90.0%) had adequate practice.

Effectiveness of the Simulation technique on stoma care related to the knowledge and Practice level of Staff Nurses: Table 3 and figure 3 shows that: The overall mean of knowledge regarding stoma care among staff nurses was 7.63 with a standard deviation of 4.16 in the pre-test, and the overall mean of knowledge regarding stoma care among staff nurses in the post-test was 18.03 with the standard deviation of 3.07.

Table 4 and figure 4 shows that: The overall mean of knowledge regarding stoma care among staff nurses was 4.08 it is a standard deviation of 2.24622 in the pre-test, and the overall mean of knowledge regarding stoma care among staff nurses in the post-test was 8.75 with the standard deviation of .99711.

Figure 3: The overall mean of knowledge regarding stoma care among staff nurses.

Figure 2: Frequency distribution of the Practice pre-test and Post-test score regarding Stoma Care among Nurses.

Figure 4: The overall mean of knowledge regarding stoma care among staff nurses.

Association between Post knowledge and Practice of the Nurses with a selected socio-demographic variable by using chi-square test: Association of socio-demographic data with practice post-test- Association of practice score

regarding stoma care with selected demographic variables such as age, gender, residence, marital status, religion, type of family, qualification, working area, working experience, income, nature of duty, duty shift, length of the duty/hours, previous knowledge regarding stoma care, previously attained stoma care training was analyzed by chi-square test. The Chi-square value of age 2.36383, tabulated value-.0.5004 at 3 degrees of freedom. Chi-square value of gender of nurses 0.233918, tabulated value-0.6286 at 1 degrees of freedom. Chi-square value of Residence, 4.87063, tabulated value 0.08757 at 2 degrees of freedom. Chi-square value of Marital status 2.33918, tabulated value 0.3112 at 2 degrees of freedom. Chi-square value of Religion 1.0582, tabulated value 0.7872, 3 degrees of freedom. The Chi-square value of types of family 0.784314, tabulated value 0.3758 at 1 degrees of freedom. Chi-square value of Qualification of nurses 0.95679, tabulated value- 0.6198 at 2 degree of freedom. Chi-square value of Working area 5.2, tabulated value 0.07427 at 2 degree of freedom. Chi-square value of Working experience 2.54902, tabulated value 0.4665 at 3 degree of freedom. Chi-square value of Income 2.83951, tabulated value 0.2418, 2 degree of freedom. The Chi-square value of Nature of duty 0.89684, tabulated value 0.6386 at 2 degree of freedom. Chi-square value of Duty shift 2.13995, tabulated value 0.1435 at 1 degree of freedom. Chi-square value of length of duty/hour is 0.00, tabulated value 0.00 at 1 degree of freedom. Chi-square value of previous knowledge regarding stoma care 2.14483, tabulated value 0.3422 at 2 degree of freedom. Chi-square value of previous attained stoma care training 4.73458, tabulated value-0.09373 at 2 degree of freedom. These values are non-significant with the socio-demographic variable.

CONCLUSION:

In the pre-test, the maximum number of 55.0% of staff nurses having poor practice regarding stoma care, 35.0% staff nurses having average practice regarding stoma care and 10.0% staff nurses having adequate practice regarding stoma care and in the post-test 90.0% of staff nurses having adequate practice regarding stoma care, 10.0% of staff nurses having average practice regarding stoma care and 0.0% of staff nurses having poor practice regarding stoma care. to the conclusion that simulation technique is effective in increasing knowledge and practice among staff nurses regarding stoma care. Hence much needs to be done in the area of hospitals and involvement of staff nurses in

this. Also emphasis on need to increasing knowledge and practice among staff nurses through simulation technique.

NURSING IMPLICATION:

In today's nursing world or health care delivery system the role and participation of nurses have changed. The findings of the study have implications in different branches of nursing that is in nursing practice, nursing education, nursing administration and nursing research, by assessing a level of staff nurse knowledge and practice regarding stoma care.

NURSING PRACTICE:

Nurses are in the best position to give information regarding various aspects of stoma care, to the patient will be free to reveal their problems to nurses. Stoma care program should organize to improve the knowledge and practice of nursing staff regarding stoma care. Nurses like other health care professionals are under increased scrutiny to provide safe and effective care.

NURSING EDUCATION:

Nursing education is developing rapidly in India and nurses from our country can be found all over the world providing care and education. The present study has implication on nursing education.

The findings of the study indicated that more emphasis should be placed in the nursing curriculum on Stoma care. Simulation technique programmes should be arranged for nurses which would be a great help for promoting themselves as well as others who are in need, this knowledge can help nurses to know about the Stoma Care with this knowledge they can explain to stoma care to the patient and. So the nurse educator must be educated knowledge regarding Stoma Care and its strategies in order to impart the knowledge and practice. Nurse educators should provide opportunities to gain knowledge and practice regarding Stoma Care.

NURSING ADMINISTRATION:

The present study reveals that there is a need to improve the knowledge and practice regarding stoma care among nursing staff, with advanced technology and ever-growing challenges of health care needs. The college and hospital administration, have a responsibility to provide nurses, nurse educators and nursing staff with continuing education on stoma care. This will enable them to update their knowledge and practice skills.

The study finding will help the administrator to arrange continuing education programme for nurses knowledge and practice regarding stoma care. It helps to prepare adequate learning material for giving health education.

NURSING RESEARCH:

The present study revealed that there is a need to improve the knowledge and practice regarding stoma care among staff nurses. The findings of the present study shall provide a baseline data for research studies to be conducted in future.

Research studies can be conducted to identify the attitude and practices towards knowledge regarding stoma care among staff nurses.

Research can be carried out to seek the effectiveness of simulation technique on knowledge and practice regarding stoma care.

LIMITATION:

Study sample is limited to 40 students. The study is limited only to staff nurses of People's Hospital in Bhopal. The present study is limited to only one group; no control group adopted for the study.

The structured knowledge and practice questionnaire and simulation technique was developed. Limited time was available for the study.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

Based on the research findings the following recommendations can be made:

The same study can be replicated on a larger sample and also at different settings for generalization of findings.

A simulation technique on knowledge and practice regarding stoma care can be prepared and given to the staff nurses, so that they can impart knowledge and practice to all people.

REFERENCES:

1. Ostomy Centres. needed to help patients post-surgery. expert, DNA India, November 19, 2013 from surgery-expert-1133879.
2. Ostomy stoma care Accessories Market size, share and industry analysis by product, B fortune business insight, march 2020. Report IDFB1102425. <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/ostomy-stoma-care-and-accessories-market-102425>.
3. Connelly T M , Khan MS, Alzamzami M, Cooke F. An evaluation of the quality and content of web-based stoma information”, PubMed, 2019;21(3):349-356. Doi: 10.1111/codi.14497. Epub 2018; 28. [https://www.Michael.F.MC.Gee.Stoma.JAMA.Patient.Page.May.2016;315\(18\):2032](https://www.Michael.F.MC.Gee.Stoma.JAMA.Patient.Page.May.2016;315(18):2032). doi: 10.1001/0202.
4. Reportlinker, The global market for Stoma/Ostomy Care Products is projected to reach US\$3.1 billion by 2025 globenewswire, August 26, 2020 <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2020/08/26/2083956/0/en/The-global-market-for-Stoma-Ostomy-Care-Products-is-projected-to-reach-US-3-1-billion-by-2025.html>
5. Sugarbaker PH. Stoma Wikipedia 16may 2022. [https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stoma_\(medicine\)](https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stoma_(medicine))
6. The Role of Stoma Nurse, Bladder & Bowel Community August 2021. <https://www.bladderandbowel.org/bowel/stoma/role-stoma-nurse/>
7. What is Simulation in nursing and why is it important”, Marquette University Nursing, July 2019. <https://mastersnursing.marquette.edu/blog/what-is-simulation-in-nursing-and-why-is-it-important/>

Cite this article as: Joshi M, Agrawal B, Gupta RR: A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Simulation Technique on Knowledge and Practice Related to Stoma Care Among Staff Nurses Working in Selected Hospital of Bhopal (M.P). PJSR. 2022;15(2):30-34.

Source of Support : Nil, Conflict of Interest: None declared.